

Matarbari Deep Sea Port: The Game Changer of Bangladesh Economy

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Abstract

Ports and shipping sector of Bangladesh are very critical for our country's sustainable economic growth. In the age of globalization, efficient infrastructure is a key factor to success. Bangladesh's government has recognized our country's great economic potential as well as the growing demand for a strong port infrastructure. After Chittagong, Mongla, and Payra port, Matarbari would be the country's fourth seaport and first deep seaport. The project's goal is to create a reliable and low-cost logistic infrastructure for seaborne cargo handling and transport services to keep the Bangladeshi products competitive in the international market. Except Matarbari, none of the deep seaport locations in the Bay of Bengal have the capacity to serve the larger hinterland region. Bangladesh is located in a strategic geographic location, with the Bay of Bengal playing a significant role in regional affairs. Bangladesh's geographic location could provide real opportunities for the country to play a major role in regional seaborne trade and serve as a gateway to the rest of the world by providing the quickest land connectivity pathway to the deepest water, saving costs and time by reducing huge distances in transportation. The deep seaport at Matarbari may also be used as a transit port for neighbors like Bhutan, Nepal, China, and India's seven sisters. Choosing Matarbari for the deep sea port location is influenced by a number of compelling geopolitical, and diplomatic considerations. Matarbari deep seaport is expected to become a transshipment port like Colombo, Singapore, and Hong Kong since it has the depth to handle larger vessels.

Keywords: Deep sea port, Economic impact, Performance

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1. Introduction

The Matarbari Port Development Project aims to establish Matarbari as a regional connectivity hub. The construction of such a mega port is intended to revolutionize the economy of the country. With docking facilities for larger vessels, the mega port has the potential to transform this region into a global economic hub that will benefit all of its users. Once it is operational, The Matarbari Port is anticipated to add 2-3 percent to the development of the national economy.[1]

2. Why a Deep Sea Port?

A deep seaport differs from a conventional port in terms of water depth. According to Ivan Roa, Polytechnic University of Catalonia, "It is considered deepsea port, one whose draft in both the entrance channel and in the terminal area, exceeds 13.72 m." [2] Both Chittagong and Mongla are too shallow for big container ships, requiring costly cargo transfers to smaller vessels. In order to move cargo in and out – an extra step is needed that adds to the cost of the port and reduces its worldwide competitiveness. Because of the maximum channel depth and berth length restrictions, no vessel longer than 190 meters or with a draft of more than 9.50 meters could approach Chittagong port.[3] Even when there is berth space available, vessels must wait for a favorable draft before berthing. The same can be said for a departing vessel that must wait for a favorable draft before leaving the port. So, for a long time, there has been a need for such a port with a wider channel to handle deep draft boats and decrease transportation costs. Correspondingly, neighboring nations, particularly landlocked countries in the area such as Nepal, Bhutan, and the Seven Sisters, using the deep sea port for their export and import trade would be beneficial.[4] All of these factors influenced Bangladesh's decision to build a deep sea port at Matarbari, Cox's Bazaar.

3. Location of the Deep Sea Port

Matarbari deep sea port is under-construction at Matarbari in Maheshkhali Upazila of Cox's Bazar District, Bangladesh.

Figure: Location map of Matarbari Deep Sea Port.[5]

4. Estimated Project Cost

Matarbari Port Development project worth Tk17,777.16 crore which will be funded by Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA), the government of Bangladesh and the Chittagong port authority. JICA will provide Tk 12,892.76 crore, the Bangladesh government Tk 2,671.15 crore and the Chittagong Port Authority Tk 2,213.94 crore.[6]

5. Port Features

The maximum permissible draft of the Matarbari deep seaport will be 16 meters.[7] It is quite encouraging compared to 9.50 meters maximum draft at Chittagong Port and 8.50 meters maximum draft of Mongla Port.[8] The Matarbari waterway will have excessive drafts so the ships will be able to land at matarbari deep seaport without having to wait for high tides at the outer port. The port will have two terminals, one of which will be 300 meters long and the other will be 460 meters long. The port will allow ships with a maximum length of 350 meters to enter where the maximum size of a ship allowed in Chittagong Port is only 190 meters.[9] At Matarbari, two jetties will be constructed having a capacity of 8,000 TUEs.[10] The jetties will let Matarbari port to handle nearly three times of the 3,000 TUEs now daily done by Chittagong Port. Matarbari port will also be used for handling coal for Matarbari coal-fired power plant.

6. Progress of the Deep Sea Port Project

One-third of the Matarbari deep seaport's construction work has been completed. The Panamanian flag carrier "Venus Triumph" became the first ship to dock at Matarbari's deep-sea port after traveling from Indonesia's Pt. Pelabuhan Cilegon Mandiri port. The authority executed an experimental capacity test of the newly built port. Because the matarbari waterway has excessive drafts, the ship was able to land at matarbari deep seaport without having to wait for high tides at the outer port. By the start of 2026, the port will be fully functional.

Figure: "Venus Triumph"-the first ship to dock at Matarbari's deep sea port.[11]

7. Matarbari Deep Sea Port-Compared to other Sea Ports of Bangladesh

Figure: Sea Ports of Bangladesh[12]

In terms of both technical and non-technical concerns, none of the existing Bangladeshi ports meet global standards. One of the major issues with existing ports is the draft problem, which prevents most big ships from entering the jetty. Those can access the jetty has to wait for high tide. Existing ports in Chittagong and Mongla are overloaded and have a shallow draft. At the moment, such ships are enforced to unload their cargo at transshipment ports in Sri Lanka and Singapore before being transported to Bangladesh by smaller vessels. As a result, there are delays and higher trade expenses for these extra steps, shipping companies demanding higher charges to recoup their costs. Ultimately putting a strain on the country's economy.

8. Matarbari Deep Sea Port-Compared to other Deep Sea Ports in the Region

Comparison of Deep Sea Ports of the Region			
Deep Sea Ports	Maximum Size of Vessel handling Capacity	Depth of Water	Cost
Matarbari, Bangladesh	70,000 DWT	16 meter	2.09 Billion US \$
Hambantota, Sri Lanka	1,00,000 DWT	17 meter	0.361 Billion US \$
Gwadar, Pakistan	2,00,000 DWT	14 meter	0.248 Billion US \$
Krishnapatnam, India	1,80,000 DWT ¹	18 meter	0.620 Billion US \$ (32.39 Billion Rupees)
Dhrama Port, India	1,80,000 DWT	17 meter	1 Billion US \$ (5200 Crore Rupees)

Figure: Comparison of Deep Sea Ports of the region.[13]

Except Matarbari, none of the deep sea port locations in the Bay of Bengal have the capacity to serve the larger hinterland region. Bangladesh's geographic location could provide real opportunities for the country to play a major role in regional seaborne trade and serve as a gateway to the rest of the world by providing the quickest land connectivity pathway to the deepest water, saving costs and time by reducing huge distances in transportation. The deep sea port at Matarbari may also be used as a transit port for neighbors like Nepal, Bhutan, China, and India's seven sisters. Matarbari deep sea port will become a transshipment port like Colombo, Singapore, and Hong Kong since it has the depth to handle larger vessels.

9. The Strength, Weakness and Benefits of Matarbari Deep Sea Port

9.1 More ports mean greater economic potential.

"About 11 % of GDP of the Netherlands is generated by the activities of the port of Rotterdam alone".[14] So, if operated effectively and efficiently, a port may function as an economic powerhouse. The globalization of the economy has resulted in a significant increase in trades of products throughout the globe. In order to keep up with the growing amount of global trade, ports in every country will undoubtedly continue to play an important role in boosting the national economy. Bangladesh's government has set a goal to become a developed country. The deep sea port will play a critical role in meeting this need by attracting more maritime-related activities.

9.2 Higher vessel size will reduce operating costs.

The current trend of most shipping companies is to build bigger ships in order to minimize operational costs. Consequently, the current three Bangladeshi ports will become obsolete after a certain period of time because all of the existing ports have the draft problem, which prevents big ships from entering the port. Economy of scale shows that the larger the ship, the lesser will be operational cost. Only a deep sea port like Matarbari will be able to facilitate this demand.

9.3 Reducing waiting time for vessels

Figure: Comparison of vessel waiting time in the region.[15]

Because the matarbari waterway will have excessive drafts, the ship will be able to land at matarbari deep seaport without having to wait for high tides at the outer port. Thus it will drastically reduce the waiting time for vessels.

9.4 Dragging Down the Cost of Doing Business

Because of all the natural and manmade limitations that all the current ports have, shipping companies demand higher rates to recoup their loss. The cost to the economy of increased shipping rates is quite significant. The expense of a shipping delay is transferred to the shippers. All of these additional expenses are ultimately shifted to the final consumer. According to USAID, reducing export processing time by five days may boost Bangladesh's GDP from \$2.4 billion to \$3.8 billion per year.[16]

9.5 Supporting Bangladesh's Economic Growth

Bangladesh is considered as one of the world's fastest growing economies, with an average annual growth rate of more than 6% for the past decade.[17] Bangladesh's economic progress is outpacing India, Sri Lanka, Nepal, and Afghanistan, according to the report of World Bank from 2019. Focusing on economic progress, Peter Clasen, the chairman of a highly respected German business delegation, labeled Bangladesh as a new “Asian Tiger”.[18] Bangladesh's textile industry is the second-most dynamic textile industry of the world. Bangladesh's export economy is expanding, and by 2021, it is anticipated to be worth more than \$50 billion per year.[19] All of this is taking place in a country that lacks appropriate maritime infrastructure. Government of Bangladesh has recognized the country's great economic potential and result of that is such a project like Matarbari.

9.6 Employment Opportunities

Matarbari port will be a big source of earning for many people. Thousands of indirect employments will be created in port-related businesses like as EPZs, SEZs, shipbuilding and repair facilities, and so on. For example, The Hambantota deep sea port of Sri Lanka has created around 10,000 direct and over 60,000 indirect new job opportunities.[19] Many businesses will benefit directly from the port. Their survival and success will be reliant on the port's existence, operations, and growth. These industries will employ millions of people and contribute significantly to the country's GDP

9.7 Direct, Indirect, and Induced Impacts.

There are three key components to determine a port's entire economic effect. These are direct, indirect, and induced effect.[14] All actions that are essential for port operation and usage are counted as direct effects. All the economic activities that are developed in the port area are referred to as an indirect effect. The indirect effects are the results of the direct effects. Direct and indirect effects on the other sides of economy are referred to as induced impacts. The sum of direct, indirect, and induced effect is the total economic effect.

9.8 Creating an Economic Zone

Bangladesh is the world's second biggest exporter of readymade garments. Keeping that in mind a special economic zone may be established near the port. Other industrial sectors will also be developed around the port. Bangladesh's government intends to provide certain incentives to international traders and to develop an industrial sector around the port area.

Conclusion

Without shipping, the global economy would collapse. Seaports are in high demand all around the world due to shipping. In the event of an industrial revolution, demand for both export and import will rapidly increase, and only a deep sea port will be able to meet this need. Given the strategic location, Bangladesh has long wished for a regional hub port like Matarbari with deep draft berths at a key position.

A port may transform a country's fate, and Bangladesh's Matarbari Deep Seaport could be one of such ports.

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